

NEW UZBEKISTAN AND TRAVEL JOURNALISM

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Abstract: The article analyzes various aspects of travel and tourism journalism, an almost unexplored sphere of journalism in Uzbekistan. Research methodology: travel journalism in Uzbekistan has undergone radical changes, a legal and regulatory framework has been created, and favourable conditions for the development of the sphere by the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage are being created. At the same time, the genre has been little studied in research papers as an important means of forming an understanding-based knowledge of travel journalism.

The article considers the current problems of travel journalism in the context of current problems of globalization and raises the questions of determining the place of this direction in the media system and the search for its history. It shows the fallacy of the attitude to travel journalism as a "meaningless" direction.

Relevant issues of special and high-quality training of travel journalists, the theory and practice of travel journalism. Special training for future travel journalists in foreign countries is currently offered mainly in the form of online classes that do not provide a serious level of training. It has been analyzed that such processes are not observed in Uzbekistan. Proposals for the inclusion of the subject "Travel Journalism" in the program of the faculties of journalism in higher educational institutions of the country are made.

Keywords: The study of travel journalism, travel, tourism, journalism genres, press tour, and travel journalism.

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НОВЫЙ УЗБЕКИСТАН И «ТРЕВЕЛ» ЖУРНАЛИСТИКА

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Abstract: В статье анализируются различные аспекты журналистики путешествий и туризма, почти неизученной области журналистики в Узбекистане. Методология исследования: в туристической журналистике Узбекистана произведены коренные изменения, создана нормативно-правовая база, создаются благоприятные условия для развития сферы Министерством туризма и культурного наследия, но жанр мало изучен в научно-исследовательских работах, как важное средство формирования основанных на понимании знаний журналистов о путешествиях.

В статье рассматриваются современные проблемы тревел-журналистики в контексте актуальных проблем глобализации, поднимаются вопросы определения места этого направления в системе СМИ и поиска его истории. Показана ошибочность отношения к тревел-журналистике как к «бессмысленному» направлению.

Поэтому актуальны вопросы специальной и качественной подготовки тревел-журналистов, изучения теории и практики тревел-журналистики. Специальная подготовка будущих журналистов-путешественников в странах дальнего зарубежья в настоящее время предлагается в основном в форме онлайн-занятий, которые не обеспечивают серьезного уровня подготовки. Проанализировано, что в Узбекистане такие процессы не наблюдаются. Также были внесены предложения о включении предмета «Выездная журналистика» в программу факультетов журналистики в высших учебных заведениях страны.

Keywords: Изучайте тревел-журналистику, путешествия, туризм, жанры журналистики, пресс-тур, тревел-журналистику.

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Abstract: Maqolada jurnalistikaning O'zbekistonda deyarli o'rganilmagan yo'nalishi - sayohat va turizm jurnalistikasining turli jihatlarini tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi O'zbekiston sayohat jurnalistikasidagi tub burilish yasaligani, normativ-huquqiy jihatdan asoslar yaratilgan, Turizm va madaniy meros vazirligi tomonidan sohani rivojlantirish uchun qulay sharoitlar yaratilayotgani, biroq janrning ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarida kam o'rganilgani, jurnalistlarning sayohat borasidagi bilimlarini shakllantirishning muhim vositasi sifatida tushunishga asoslanadi.

Ushbu yo'nalishning media tizimidagi o'rnini aniqlash va uning tarixini izlashga oid savollarni ko'targan holda, maqolada globallashuvning dolzarb muammolari kontekstida sayohat jurnalistikasining bugungi muammolariga e'tibor qaratilgan. Sayohat jurnalistikasiga "bema'ni" yo'nalish sifatida yondashishning noto'g'riligi ko'rsatilgan.

Shu bois sayyohlik jurnalistlarini maxsus va sifatli tayyorlash, sayohat jurnalistikasi nazariyasi va amaliyotini o'rganish masalalari dolzarb hisoblanadi. Bo'lajak sayyohlik jurnalistlari uchun maxsus treninglar xorijiy mamlakatlarda hozirda asosan onlayn darslar ko'rinishida taklif etilmoqda, bu esa jiddiy tayyorgarlik darajasini ta'minlamaydi. O'zbekistonda esa bunday jarayonlar kuzatilmayotgani tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, mamlakat oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jurnalistika fakultetlarida "traveling journalism" o'quv fanini dasturga kiritish bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.

Keywords: Sayohat jurnalistikasi, sayohat, turizm, jurnalistika janrlari, press-tur, sayohat jurnalistikasini o'rganish.

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It would not be wrong to say that the genre known as "travel journalism" in the international sphere of travel journalism is literally in its first stages of development in Uzbekistan. Until today, travel essays and articles related to travel have been published on various pages of the press, and various programs have been produced on television. Today, however, the genre of travel journalism is taking on a new dimension in modern tourism.

At first, when talking about this genre, many people imagined it as travelling somewhere for fun and simply telling what they saw. However, this genre requires good skills, knowledge and physical strength on the part of the journalist. The famous African travel journalist David Livingstone said, "It is much easier to travel than to describe it."¹⁴⁸

Indeed, the creation of programs of this genre on television is not an easy task. Not only speed, mobility, and great organizational effort are required of the journalist, but also knowledge of the geography, peculiarities, traditions, history, and culture of different countries of the world. "A travel journalist explores the world to share his knowledge with others. He constantly collects information, communicates with local people, and does not use the services of the usual travel packages and traditional tourist itineraries. He tends to move around on his own. Being on your presents some challenges, but this approach allows you to get off the beaten path and make unique discoveries"¹⁴⁹.

¹⁴⁸ Livingstone D. Travels and explorations in South Africa from 1840 to 1855 / David Livingstone. Moscow "Geografiz" Publishing house, 1955, p.7

¹⁴⁹ Pokanzieva I. Проблемное поле трэвел-журналистики как явления современного медиапространства (The problematic field of travel journalism as a phenomenon of modern media space.): URL: <http://www.geografia.ru>

Today's modern travel media products globally include a variety of genres. Some theorists in informal circles call it a program that is produced without any order, not adhering to journalistic genres. However, these thoughts are misplaced. Travel journalism is a hybrid of the brightest and most interesting genres.

Historically, geography shows have been associated with science documentaries, travel narratives and educational lecture films. As a modern television genre, they combine elements of documentaries, educational programming, entertainment talk shows, reality shows, soap operas, and commercials.

The presenter of such programs now travels with the viewer to a new destination with some regularity. The creative and sometimes acting ability of the presenter plays an important role in this: he is responsible for the audiovisual product as a provider of positive information and good humour.

Modern travel programs are characterized by two trends: 1. Specific targeting combined with the format of the program (teenagers and young people, travellers, housewives, etc.); 2. The emphasis of the population is on presenters, often well-known personalities - actors, showmen, politicians, and businessmen.

In short, the conceptual balance "us"/"them" that existed previously in the programs gives way to the formula "us among them."¹⁵⁰

For example, a program host goes to a certain place, studies the customs and values of the inhabitants of that place, and tries to assimilate among the people. If he connects every situation he encounters with his view, the program becomes a piece built on personal opinion. For example, Shakhdzhakhan Karimov, the author of "Borib koramiz", (Let's go and see) which 2022 was broadcast on "Dunyo boylab" TV channel and is now presented to viewers on the "Mahalla" TV channel will go on a trip around Uzbekistan. The host travels to far-flung places that the channel's staff and journalists can't get to. Conducts very friendly conversations with residents. He listens to stories about values and morals, unknown to the townspeople. This style characterizes the style of "us among them".

In general, Uzbek TV channels in recent years have made a big step in travel journalism. This is a direct result of dozens of decisions and decrees of the head of state to develop domestic and foreign tourism in the country. In particular, according to the Presidential Decree of February 3, 2018 "On additional organizational measures to create favourable conditions for the development of tourist potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the TV channel "**Dunyo Boylab**" (Around the world) of the National TV and Radio Company of Uzbekistan State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (now Ministry

¹⁵⁰ . Pokazanieva I. V. Проблемное поле трэвел-журналистики как явления современного медиапространства (The problematic field of travel journalism as a phenomenon of modern media space:) [Digital source]: V. Pokazanieva // Mediascope. — 2013. — Vol 3. — Access mode:<http://www.mediascope.ru/node/1385>.

of Tourism and Cultural Heritage) is responsible for the development of domestic tourism, active leisure and sports tourism, conservation and use of cultural heritage sites and natural resources. This brought about a radical change in tourism journalism in Uzbekistan.

After this Decree, the number of travel and tourism-related television programs in the broadcasting program of the TV channel "Dunyo Boylab" (Around the world) sharply increased. For example, the program "Turizm yangiliklar" (Tourism News) (15 minutes) aired daily at 2:00 pm and at 7:00 pm regularly five days a week brought to the viewers the news of tourism in Uzbekistan. In addition, through the program "Turizm tahlil" (Analysis of Tourism) the content of our country's tourism reforms, tourism development, and discussion of new ideas with the participation of experts was another bold step in travel and tourism journalism.

about 30 programs like "Telesayohat" ("TV-travel", Author: all employees of the channel), "Borib ko'ramiz" ("Let's see", Author: Shakhjahan Karimov), "Ziyorat" ("Pilgrimage", Author: Fayziddin Mukhiddinov), "Yol-boylab" ("By the way", Author: Rahmatilla Sattorov), "Dunyo Oshxonasi" ("World Cuisine", Author: Shahnoza Nurmatova), "Sairbon" ("Traveller", Author: Sharofiddin Husniddinov), "Sarguzasht izlab" and ("Adventure" and "Joyful vacation", Author: Sunnatilla Gulomov), as well as "Agrotourism" (Author: Dildora Abdukarimova), "Baliq ovi" (Fishing, Author: Ibragim Saparov) are evidence of the revival of travel journalism in Uzbekistan. In addition, a good revolution in travel journalism was the travel programs presented on 14 regional TV channels and more than 18 private TV channels under the management of the National TV and Radio Company.

As a practical result of the reforms carried out in the field of tourism by the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, the direct participation of journalists in sites and organized festivals can be called a step forward in "travel" journalism in Uzbekistan. In particular, **in 2021 a total of 23 press tours for media representatives working in the field of tourism in our country and abroad were organized. In the first half of 2022 19 press tours were organized.**¹⁵¹

Inviting Uzbekistan and preparation of several materials, certainly, along with the wide popularization of tourism in our country, also created the space for an exchange of ideas and experience with local journalists. Journalists from abroad mostly talked about the monuments of historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent and Shakhrisabz, when almost all journalists from Uzbekistan, working in the field of travel, have visited these cities or prepared material about them. In this case, the media of our country helped to observe the creative activities of foreign journalists and get acquainted with their approach to

¹⁵¹ Response letter of the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage No. 02-08/3520 dated July 18, 2022 on the appeal No. 86557-c/22 dated July 3, 2022, received through the website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

the same topic. Each journalist has his or her vision and attitude to the subject. For example, a story about Registan Square in the work of a hundred journalists will be presented differently. In particular, someone draws attention to its beauty, someone draws attention to the fact that today it has turned into a beautiful alley. Another journalist will talk about its great history.

After the simplification of the system of entry (visa) of foreign citizens into our country, the number of journalists among foreign tourists arriving in Uzbekistan has increased significantly compared to 2017. Specifically, about 100 foreign journalists came to our country in 2017, and in 2018 that number was more than 220. A total of 419 journalists and bloggers visited our country in 2019. This year that number is expected to exceed 1,000 people.¹⁵²

A special role in the organization of such press tours is played by the "National PR Center" PE. The history of the creation of the organization begins in 2018 - when the government of Uzbekistan decided to show the world the beauty of our country, the uniqueness of its ancient cities and the unexplored routes. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018 "On additional organizational measures to create favourable conditions for the development of the tourist potential of the Republic¹⁵³ of Uzbekistan" № PF-5326 Uzbekistan under the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (now the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan), the "National PR Center" of DUK was established. This decision is a new vision of expanding the huge tourism potential of the country, creating an entirely new brand of Uzbekistan and promoting it abroad.

There are many such examples. In particular, by the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 31/40-11 dated April 29, 2021, the representatives of the Russian TV channel "REN TV" visited our country on May 8-15, 2021.

The members of the delegation visited the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm regions and the city of Tashkent to shoot the next issue of the TV program "Невероятно интересные истории" (Incredibly interesting stories) on "REN TV" channel, created a program devoted to the objects of tourist, natural, sports and cultural significance in our country, and to expand the flow of foreign tourists to our country.

By the letter № 09/14992 of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 4, 2022, representatives of the Belgian "Eccholine" and Hungarian television company "TV-2" (108 people in total) visited our country from 7-13 June 2022. In this regard, the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage has

¹⁵² Response letter of the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage No. 02-08/3520 dated July 18, 2022 on the appeal No. 86557-c/22 dated July 3, 2022, received through the website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
¹⁵³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3548467>

developed a draft program for staying in the country and submitted it for approval to the Cabinet of Ministers.

The purpose of the visit is to shoot the 3rd season of the show "Asia Express" in Uzbekistan for a large Hungarian entertainment company "TV-2".

The creative group consisting of representatives of the Turkish Broadcasting Company ("TRT", "BrandAge", "Daily Sabah", "Haberturk", "Sabah", "TRT Russian", "GZT", "NTV", "Milliet", "AjansHabr", "TVNET") participating in the international scientific conference on "The role of the Kokan Khanate in the formation and cultural heritage of the statehood of the Turkic peoples", held in the city of Kokand June 7-10, 2022", participation was organized in the established order.

According to the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 31/40-8 from April 1, 2022, the documentary film "Globe-pecheurs en Uzbekistan" for the French TV channel "Chasse et Peche TV" the visit of the creative group to the country for filming and shooting was organized at a high level.

According to the order of the Secretary of the Security Council under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № XDFU-I-1-PA 1-6343 of May 12, 2022, a group of bloggers and major tourist organizations from the Baltic and Scandinavian countries (25 people in total) Visits Samarkand, Bukhara and Khorezm regions of our republic and Tashkent city on May 16-23 were organized at a high level.

The planned trip of a creative group of "Russia-24" TV channel (2 people) to Uzbekistan on February 10-18 this year was organized at a high level by the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage and provided them with practical assistance.

Another important point is that as a result of the successful development of travel journalism, the Uzbek TV channels need to train journalists who can conduct large-scale television projects. None of the faculties of journalism at our republic's leading universities offers travel journalism courses or has introduced academic subjects. The opening of a faculty of tourism journalism at the Silk Road International Tourism University in Samarkand from the academic year 2020/2021 was reported in the newspaper New Uzbekistan and on its official website.¹⁵⁴ Later, however, the issue was simply left open.

In our opinion, there are other serious problems associated with the development of the thematic direction of travel journalism. The analysis of modern local history programs has shown that the popular science content in such programs is losing its importance. At present, the audience demands the journalist present interesting situations, in short, to be spectacular.

¹⁵⁴ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/samarqandda-sayohat-jurnalistikasi-fakulteti-ochiladi>

For this reason, authors now pay more and more attention to showing attractions, entertainment, and advertising components, and under such conditions "modern science-popular television" is developing. The dominance of "infotainment" projects is increasing, and convergence processes are taking place. Due to the emergence of various television shows and entertainment programs, the number of genres of travel television journalism is also increasing.

In Volume IX of Nargis Kasimova's book "Specialized Journalism," which is being prepared for publication under the guidance of the AOCA of Uzbekistan, the Journey author team emphasizes that modern travel programs consist of a hybrid of genres. For example, a single historical and geographical program combines elements of a documentary, travel narrative and educational program¹⁵⁵.

In our opinion, this idea is wrong. The reason is that "travel journalism" is a separate, independent genre. So is the genre "Reportage. We know that reportage can consist of elements of interview, conversation, investigative journalism and journalism. However, in modern journalism, it is considered a separate genre. Similarly, even if travel journalism consists of the aforementioned elements, we believe it should be accepted as a hybrid genre.

Because of these controversial situations, there is a need to study this genre both academically and practically. Over the past 25 years, there has been a great deal of research in the West. Monographs and articles have been published.

In the West (from England to Australia), travel journalism as a subject is mainly available in various online schools, and it has become a very popular area of "distance" education. However, there are also institutional centres for the study and teaching of travel journalism. These include the Center for the Study of Travel Literature at Nottingham Trent University (England), the Institute for Advanced Study at Cambridge University, the London School of Journalism evening courses in travel journalism, and the Mass Communication major at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece). My first experience of teaching travel journalism in Russia began in 2004-2013 as a special course and creative studio at the journalism department of Moscow State University. Today in Russia, travel journalism as a subject can be found in the programs of some educational institutions. Commercial "travel journalism schools" have also appeared. They conduct training without a clear methodology or program, often in the form of distant online classes and at an amateur level. Some training courses are held in the form of "circles of interest" as travellers gather over a cup of tea to share their experiences.¹⁵⁶ In our country, there

¹⁵⁵ Qosimova N. (Preparation for publication) Specialized Journalism Volume IX. Tashkent, "Uzbekistan" Publishing house, 2019. p.542

¹⁵⁶ Krivtsov N. Трэвел-журналистика: специфика направления и его проблемы (Travel journalism: the specifics of the sphere and its issues). Вопросы теории и практики журналистики (Issues in the Theory and Practice of Journalism). 2017. Tashkent 6. Vol. 3 p. 360-361

are no training courses or special subjects aimed at a serious study of the theory and practice of travel journalism.

From the foregoing it is natural to conclude that it is necessary to take travel journalism more seriously, to study in depth the various aspects and problems of this field, as well as to train those who want to devote themselves to travel journalism.

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7. <https://lex.uz/docs/-3548467>
8. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/samarqandda-sayohat-jurnalistikasi-fakulteti-ochiladi>